
92. Diffuse interstellar bands

INTERSTELLAR ‘EXTINCTION’ occurs because of the absorption and scattering of electromagnetic radiation by dust and gas in the interstellar medium lying between source and observer (for Gaia, in space, we can ignore the additional effects of Earth’s atmosphere!).

For stars lying near to the Galactic plane, and within a few kpc of the Sun, extinction in the visible amounts to about 1.8 mag per kiloparsec. Shorter wavelengths being more strongly attenuated, extinction causes objects to appear redder than their intrinsic spectrum would suggest, an effect referred to as interstellar ‘reddening’.

While the effect of extinction is a reasonably smooth function of wavelength, superimposed on its general shape are absorption features that can have a variety of origins, and which can give clues as to the chemical composition of the interstellar gas and dust grains. Prominent absorption features include a pronounced bump at 217.5 nm (in the ultraviolet), a water ice feature at 3.1 μm , and silicate features at 10 and 18 μm .

For Gaia, the effects of extinction and reddening can be estimated for *each source* as part of the astrophysical parameter determination, using the RP and BP spectra, and the radial velocity spectra (see essay #89). This is allowing the construction of a detailed all-sky map of interstellar extinction, which I will describe elsewhere.

DIFFUSE INTERSTELLAR BANDS, DIBs, are additional absorption features seen in stellar spectra, first reported just over a century ago, but whose detailed origins still remains something of a mystery. Their wavelengths do not correspond with any known (ion or molecular) spectral lines, and so the material which is responsible for the absorption cannot easily be identified.

Their name further conveys the fact that DIBs are conspicuously broader than interstellar atomic lines, presumably due to unresolved rotational structure.

In his review, Herbig (1995) summarised the status at the time by noting that of the 127 confirmed DIBs in the region between 0.4–1.3 μm , only two had been (tentatively) identified with a specific ‘carrier’. Around 600 bands have now been discovered, at ultraviolet, visible and infrared wavelengths (Fan et al. 2019).

Because DIB strengths increase roughly in proportion to colour excess, they were originally suspected as being produced by interstellar grains. But current evidence favours unknown species of free polyatomic molecules, such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and other large C-bearing molecules, either neutral or ionised. Today, only one carrier is securely identified: ionised buckminsterfullerene (C_{60}^+), with five absorption bands in the near-infrared (Linnartz et al. 2020).

One important observational result, established pre-Gaia, is that the strengths of most DIBs are not strongly correlated with each other. This means that there must be many carriers, rather than one carrier responsible for all DIBs. Also significant is that the strength of DIBs is broadly correlated with the interstellar extinction, even though they are unlikely to be caused by dust grains.

THE CHOICE OF WAVELENGTH range for Gaia’s radial velocity spectrometer was driven by a number of considerations, which I summarised in my essay #85. Amongst these, and within the adopted wavelength range (845–872 nm), was a known medium-intensity diffuse interstellar band at 862 nm, first identified in 1975. The correlation of its equivalent width with absorption was known to be rather tight, suggesting that it could be used as one of the indicators to build a detailed reddening map, especially for high values of interstellar extinction (Munari 1999).

The figure is an example RVS spectrum of one Gaia star from DR3 in the wavelength region of the DIB feature. The difference between the observed spectrum (blue line), and the best-fit synthetic spectrum (orange line) brings out the DIB feature as shown in the inset.

THE 862 nm diffuse interstellar band is characterised as part of the GSP-Spec module, which I described briefly in essay #89. In addition to the equivalent widths and their uncertainties, the tabulations in DR3 list their characteristic central wavelength, line width, and various quality flags (Recio-Blanco et al. 2022).

The first major study of the 862 nm DIB in Gaia DR3 has been reported by Schultheis et al. (2022); they also review the pre-Gaia work on this specific feature (notably with RAVE), which I will not discuss further.

Their sample contains 476 117 stars with valid DIB measurements, with their high-quality sample comprising 141 103 stars. The former is, by an order of magnitude, the largest homogeneous full-sky sample obtained so far. The distribution, given here in Galactic coordinates, shows that stars with a significant DIB feature are concentrated towards the Galactic plane, as expected, but with significant sub-structure.

IN THESE TWO ‘Kiel diagrams’, which are analogues of the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram showing the star’s surface gravity versus effective temperature, i.e. $\log(g)$ vs T_{eff} , the first is colour-coded as a function of the absorption feature’s equivalent width, and the second according to stellar distances. The very similar trends in both diagrams is striking, and clearly indicates that stars with larger distances have larger equivalent widths.

By also showing that massive stars at 2–4 kpc distance are located in the most nearby spiral arms (notably the Sagittarius/Carina, Local and Perseus arms), they were also able to demonstrate that the 862 nm line provides an excellent tracer of spiral arm structures.

THE EQUIVALENT WIDTHS are also generally well-correlated with estimates of interstellar reddening (with $E(\text{BP}-\text{RP})$ derived from the Gaia BP/RP spectra by the GSP-Phot module), with both showing larger values in the Galactic plane.

But they also drew attention to some notable differences, in particular that the scale height of the 862 nm carrier is smaller than that of the dust, and that it is concentrated within the inner kpc from the Sun.

Another striking difference between the 862 nm DIB carrier and dust distributions is that the former features are present in the Local Bubble around the Sun, even though this region is known to contain almost no dust.

To first order, they found that the spatial distribution of the 862 nm DIB follows a simple slab model. They derived its local density and scale height, which can be used to predict its expected equivalent width towards any star up to about 3 kpc from the Sun. Specifically, they determined a local density of $0.019 \pm 0.004 \text{ nm/kpc}$, and a scale height of $98.6^{+11.1}_{-8.5} \text{ pc}$. The latter, being smaller than the dust scale height, indicates that the DIBs are more concentrated towards the Galactic plane.

FINALLY, taking advantage of the full sky coverage, they determined its rest-wavelength in the Galactic anticentre direction, yielding $\lambda_0 = 862.086 \pm 0.0019 \text{ nm}$, the most precise determination to date.

Based on this rest-wavelength, the Galactic rotation curve within 1–2 kpc from the Sun shows a remarkably good agreement between the 862 nm diffuse interstellar band velocities and the CO gas velocities, reinforcing the suggestion that the associated carrier(s) could be related to gaseous macromolecules.

STUDIES OF THE correlation between different diffuse interstellar bands are important for gaining insight into their origin. Although the strong line at 862 nm was the only confirmed DIB in Gaia’s RVS spectral range, Munari et al. (2008) considered a weaker one at 864.8 nm to be a second promising candidate.

From 8458 DR3 spectra, Zhao et al. (2022) confirmed its existence, and showed that both equivalent widths are well correlated, albeit with the 862 nm line being better correlated with the $E(\text{BP}-\text{RP})$ extinction measure.